

HISTORICAL AND POLITICAL CONDITIONS PRIOR TO THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE NATIONAL STATE: INTENTION OF THE NATIONAL IDEOLOGICAL STRUGGLE

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Abstract

M.A.Rasulzada, who entered the world of politics at the beginning of the 20th century, came to the forefront of the struggle with the idea of independence and the love of freedom. His greatest work and goal was freedom for people and independence for nations.

M.A.Rasulzada came to the public environment with literary and poetic thinking. When he said, "A flag once raised will never falls" he meant the idea of independence. All his subsequent activity in 1920 was that he did not let the light of independence go out in exile. Rasulzada created the political legacy of the idea of independence.

M.A.Rasulzada is one of the founders of the Azerbaijani national independence movement, which is the first republican administration of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, not only in the regions where Turks exist, but in the entire Islamic world. M.A.Rasulzada rendered great historical services in the ways of restoring the centuries-old statehood traditions of our people and spreading the ideas of independence.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the national-political awakening and the unification in the format of a political party were related to the Musavat faction. In this first phase, the Musavat Party tried to unite the Muslim and Turkic-speaking nations living in the Russian Empire and the Middle East around the ideas of national freedom and democratic autonomy.

Keywords: National, statehood, historical-political, struggle, ideology.

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Muhammad Amin Rasulzadeh, a prominent socio-political figure of Azerbaijan, the leader of our independence struggle, one of the founders of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, was born on January 31, 1884 in Novkhani village of Baku. Muhammad Amin's father was a religious figure deeply committed to Islamic doctrine. His father, who was a clergyman, sent his son to the second "Russian-Muslim" school headed by Sultan Majid Ganizade, a famous pedagogue of the time, bright and intelligent. After graduating from this school, Muhammad Amin continued his education at

the Baku Technical School. However, he left this school without completing his education. leaves and then starts to engage in social and political activities. In 1903, M.A. Rasulzade created the association of Young revolutionaries with the participation of several students [10.p.14.].

This organization operates secretly, its main goal was to promote Turkishness, to educate young people and acquire national ideas, and to promote freedom and revolutionary work among workers. "Hummat" newspaper helped them in all aspects [13.sah.17.]. Inspired by the first political steps, young people clearly felt the importance and necessity of political organization.

In 1904, on the basis of the Muslim Democratic Musavat society, the Muslim Social Democratic Hummet organization was established under the Baku committee of the Russian Social Democratic Labor Party [3. p. 328.]. This organization was founded by people like Muhammad Amin Rasulzade, Muhammad Hasan Hajinski, Mashadi Azizbayov and Nariman Narimanov.

2024 marks the 140th anniversary of the birth of the prominent social and political figure, one of the founders of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, Chairman of the Azerbaijan National Council, Muhammad Amin Rasulzadeh.

In the decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, dated December 30, 2023, it is stated: "Mohammed Amin Rasulzadeh is one of the personalities who rendered great services to the realization of the ideas of independence and the revival of the national state structure in Azerbaijan in the first decades of the 20th century in the crisis geopolitical conditions. His ideology of independence took its source from the idea of national freedom rooted in the centuries-old memory of his native people. Mohammad Amin Rasulzade's brilliant journalistic, political, literary-critical and scientific legacy, which became the

chronicle of the era, occupies a special place in the history of public opinion of Azerbaijan. For many years, even in exile, he lived and fought with the dream of an independent Azerbaijan" [4.].

Prominent historians and researchers of the republic period have done important work in collecting and systematizing the works of the great thinker. For example, prominent historical scientist, prof. The collection prepared by Nasiman Yagublu as editor and author of the foreword [5.] is very interesting. The emigration stages of Rasalzade's works are also systematized in this collection. His works, which will include works from 1920 to 1955 and span 10 volumes, are divided into different periods.

1. Turkey period: 1922-1929 years (published books and articles, speeches)
2. European period: France, Germany, Poland 1929-1939 years.
3. Romania-Germany: 1940-1947 years
4. Turkey period: 1948-1955 years

Thus, M.A. Rasalzade was active in social, political and press work in each of the countries he was in exile (including Turkey and European countries France-Poland-Germany and Romania) [5.p.12.].

Rasalzadeh's participation in the Mashruta movement that took place in Iran in 1908-1911 and his social and political activities: his writings, the preparation, distribution, and publication of revolutionary leaflets, and later these writings were written in Turkey in 1911 in "The Turks of Iran" in volume I of his works in 1911 (1903-1909; Baku, 1992) and II volume (1909-1914; Baku, 2001) [5. p. 12.].

Also, in 1911, another book by M.A. Rasalzadeh in Persian language "The Happiness of Mankind" was published in Ardabil. It is clear that the leftist ideas of the great writer still remain in this work.

The course and scope of the current revolution in Iran are seriously alarming some states (Czarist Russia, Great Britain, etc. - I.K.) and they are taking a number of steps. The tsarist government demands the expulsion of the left-leaning Russian subjects participating in Iran from the Tehran government. M.A. Rasalzade was among them. Rasalzade's multifaceted activity was noticeable in the Mashruta movement. He was active in igniting the revolution and weakening the position of Tsarist Russia here. M.A. Rasalzadeh was forced to leave Iran in May 1911 and go to Istanbul. During the mentioned period, people who escaped the persecution of tsarism found refuge in Istanbul. In the later periods, those political immigrants, first of all, Azerbaijanis Ali Bey Huseynzade, Ahmed Bey Agoglu, and Yusif Akchurali had undeniable services in the formation of Turkism around an idea. It is no coincidence that the Russian historian and diplomat A. Mandelshtarm considered these people together with Ismayil Gaspraly as the "creators of the ideology of Turkism" [2. p. 7.].

After this period, the change of M.A. Rasalzadeh's political and ideological views from socialism to nationalism accelerated, especially as a result of the rise of Turkism. Reanalyzing and evaluating the path of political struggle, M.A. Rasalzade finally comes to the conclusion that these ideas (socialism - I.K.) as a whole do not meet the requirements of the national liberation ideas of Azerbaijani Turks. Although Rasalzade was

young, he was a very talented person who could open up new ideas and speak for himself in all matters. A series of articles "Iranian Turks" was published in a hot period of Turkism. It was the first fundamental article of the Turkish communities here, specifically introducing the Azerbaijani Turkishness to the Turkish common thought [6.]. In 1906-1907, M.A. Rasalzade wrote in "Takamul" as well as in other press organizations demanding equality of rights and freedom for nations, tribes, classes, people (individuals) and over time these political students were called "Freedom to people, independence to nations". !” was formed as a call.

The great Azerbaijani thinker learns the "Vahdati jinsiyya philosophy" ("Philosophy of National Unity") of Sheikh Jamaledin Afghani, translates it from Persian into Turkish and publishes it in "Turkish Land".

In 1913, after the amnesty granted in connection with the 300th anniversary of the Romanov dynasty, Rasalzade returned to Baku. The "Muslim Democratic Party", "Musavat" was founded in October 1911 by M.A. Rasalzade's close allies, Mammadali Rasalzade (I.K. was his cousin), Abbasgulu Kazimzade, and Taghi Naghioglu. At that time, M.A. Rasalzade was still in exile in Turkey. However, after returning from exile, the leadership of the party was transferred to him. Wherever he was, this phenomenal personality tirelessly formed a very rich, conceptual, important for all time, thought-provoking, visionary concept, idea, strategic road map.

In 1915, he published the newspaper "Achiq soz-Open word". He fights for the purity of the Azerbaijani language, writes a series of articles under the title "National vitality" in the journal "Dirilik" (1914-1916) [1.p.302.]. In the series of articles entitled "National Vitality", M.A. Rasalzade gave a broad explanation of the concepts of "Ummat" and "Nation", showing that the word "Ummat" has a purely religious meaning and means the confessional unity of all Muslims of the world, regardless of ethnic and cultural affiliation. However, the nation is not a religion, but an ethnic unity [9. p. 468.]. In fact, as we mentioned above, the influence of Jalaluddin Afghani's views was felt in Rasalzadeh's thoughts (regarding religious issues - I.K.), that is, he considered religion as a secondary component, even though he included it among the characteristics of nations. He reasoned that religion is a less stable sign because "in history there are nations that have changed many religions." Continuing his opinion, he writes: "Language is permanent, remains, even though it progresses and evolves, it does not undergo a fundamental change or change" [9. p. 468.].

M.A. Rasalzade in his article ("National Vitality") shows the three-level ethnic associations and gives a detailed explanation. "Ethnicity, nationality and nation. He also explained the differences in their form and quality. "Nationality-narodnost" included only the unity of generation and language. In such an example, he showed: "It can be attributed to a small tribe and ethnic-ethnic press that grew up from one middle grandfather and spoke the same language. As for the Second Nationality, here, in contrast to nationality, the factor of blood kinship loses its importance for the nationality, and the unity of language and culture comes to the fore. M.A. Rasalzadeh wrote that "Nation-language unity,

custom and moral unity, traditional-historical and finally faith-secular unity is an organized product" [9. p. 469.].

Rasulzade saw the main difference between nationality and nation in the fact that the individuals who make up the nation have a national self-consciousness. In the mentioned period, the national self-consciousness of the people was not properly formed. Therefore, the intellectuals of the time attached special importance to the formation of national ideology. M.A. Rasulzade suggested that the formation of the national consciousness of the Azerbaijani Turks should begin with the restoration of the people's historical memory. He showed that a factor of unity and cultural development as strong as a nation's knowledge of its history cannot be imagined [8. p. 18.].

M.A. Rasulzade recommended giving special importance to the development of national language in the process of awakening and progress of condemned nationalities, including Azerbaijani Turks. In order to enrich the national literary language, he advised to turn to the spoken language of the Azerbaijani Turks, rather than to related Turkic languages. This was the first horizon, the sign of Azerbaijan's national identity.

M.A. Rasulzadeh wrote that only "national independence is able to ensure the protection of the characteristics of nations" [9. p. 466.]. He systematically expressed the course of events in his thoughts and writings and wrote in the first issue of "Açıq soz" newspaper: "He emphasized the need to create a national state in order to transition from the status of nationality to the level of nation." Making his opinion a little more concrete, he came to the conclusion that "It is a nationality that insists on becoming a nation-state" [8. p. 20.].

As we know, until the October revolution, M.A. Rasulzade did not declare the idea of creating a national state in one form or another. There were a number of objective and subjective reasons for this. Because only the declaration of political slogans required the existence of minimum freedoms. As the Russian tsarism knew the special sympathy of the Azerbaijani Turks for the Ottomans, it behaved mercilessly on the basis of the smallest excuses, especially the insincere attitude towards the national forces. Commenting on the reasons for the weakening and fall of the tsarist absolutism, Rasulzadeh wrote that "the revolution emerged from the overflow of two important forces that pressured the empire from within. On the one hand, the deprived classes and on the other hand, the condemned nations wanted the truth" [7. p. 28.].

The first political program of the Azerbaijani national movement was adopted at the Pan-Caucasus Muslim Congress held in Baku on April 15-20, 1917, after the February Revolution. Various socio-political groups were represented at this congress. However, M.A. Rasulzade, who at that time had already become one of the main figures of the national movement, played a decisive role in determining the political goals of the Azerbaijani Turks. He was also assigned to make a report at this congress. The ideas put forward by M.A. Rasulzade in his deep report with conceptual content at the congress determined the political goals of the Azer-

bajani national movement for the near future. Azerbaijan's national freedom is understood at least by the political elite, these prominent thinkers directed their further activities in this direction. In this idea, it was clear that the political elite was a manifestation of the transition from Turkism to Azerbaijanism. M.A. Rasulzade once again reminded that the main sign of the nation is not religion, but "unity of language, unity of history, unity of customs and traditions" [11. P. 164.].

On the issue of the future state administration of Russia, the representatives of the two currents opposing each other faced each other in terms of differences of opinion at the All-Russian Muslim Congress held in Moscow from May 1 to 11, 1917. Ahmad Salikov, who delivered the main speech on behalf of the unitarians at the congress, did not deny the importance of national state building. In fact, his opinion was dominated by such a wrong trend that the Muslims of Russia are backward, so they do not have the opportunity to create such a state. At the end of the speech, he came to the conclusion that if there is only one way to solve the issue of nationality of Muslims in Russia, it is the method of giving Muslims cultural autonomy based on individuality" [11. p. 147.].

At this congress, M.A. Rasulzade, who was distinguished and remembered for his brilliant speeches, proposals, and ideas, speaking from the position of the Azerbaijani National Movement, justified with concrete facts that the approach of the unitarians, led by A. Salikov, to the national problems of the Russian Muslims is wrong. M.A. Rasulzade expressed a reasoned opinion that the views, approaches, and arguments of the universities regarding the concept of "Nation" and the solution of the national issue as a whole are wrong: "Sometimes they say that Islam itself is a nation. They say that Islam, in spite of Christianity, makes Muslims a nation, because if you ask any Turk what he is, and if you say what nationality you are, he will answer you as a Muslim. But this theory is wrong. Unfortunately, this wrong tendency is propagated by the Iranian-Persian regime against a fragmented and divided part of our nation in the south, which is our historical territory. Also, the great ideologist reminded that the main sign of the nation is not religion, but unity of language, unity of history, unity of customs and traditions" [11. p. 164.]. This speech of M.A. Rasulzade shows that the process of separation of the national identity of the Azerbaijani Turks from the all-Muslim and all-Turk slogan has already become inevitable. Rasulzade's position was accepted by the majority of the congress participants.

At the plenary session of the Congress on May 7, 1917, the draft resolution prepared by M.A. Rasulzadeh was adopted by a majority (446 votes in favor and 271 votes against). Thus, the idea of transforming Russia into a federal republic consisting of separate national-territorial autonomies, the project of forming the country's Turkic-Muslim peoples as separate independent nations won [12.p.11.].

In a word, the path to Azerbaijan's independence has gone through such hard struggles and struggles. M.A. Rasulzade is not only the architect of the national statehood of Azerbaijani Turks, but also its founder. He is a statesman who made invaluable contributions to the

establishment and development of the republic that existed in 1918-1920. In our next study, we will try to talk about the directions of studying M.A. Rasalzade's rich statecraft. A continuation of the first article dedicated to the 140th anniversary of the great leader's birth is also planned.

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